

Assessing Gujarat's Progress on SDG-10: An Economic Perspective

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Abstract—This paper provides a brief theoretical discussion on Sustainable Development Goal 10 (Reduced Inequalities) relating to Gujarat. Inequality itself is multidimensional as it spans across various indicators. SDG-10 has a conceptual and empirical challenge since the target indicators are not easy to measure, specially when investigating for these indicators at zonal or regional levels. In Gujarat there has been significant economic growth, but the picture would be incomplete without understanding the dynamics of income distribution. Due to the lack of relevant disaggregated state-level data across many of the ten targets and accompanying indicators, and their relevance, our approach is conceptual. This paper briefly discusses some of the the major dimensions of inequalities as outlined by the SDG 10 targets and provides insights about their existing situation in the state. The attempt is to contribute to the existing studies on SDG-10 progress in the state and present the socio-economic foundation of the various indicators laid under the goal.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Inequalities, Economic Disparity

I. INTRODUCTION

SDG 10 talks about the urgent need to reduce disparities within and among countries. This goal recognizes that globally countries continue to face inequality based on income, wealth, opportunity and that social inclusion hinders the efforts to sustainable and inclusive development. It points out that the pandemic has worsened the existing inequalities between the countries. Discrimination based on sex have been twice as for women than for men. (UN SDG, n.d.) The progress indicators also showed that the year 2023 “marked a record high of 35.8 million refugees, and over 8,000 migrant deaths were recorded globally.” The target indicators spanned across several sub-targets to measure it with respect to different sections of the society.

The core focus of this goal is to reduce economic inequality, or disparity in the distribution of economic resource and opportunity, will negatively affect the ability to achieve sustainable development Economic inequality indicates the disparity in the distribution of economic resources, among individuals or households, that make up a defined population.

Economic Inequality includes two sub-categories: income inequality and wealth inequality. Income inequality refers to the disparity in the amounts earned by in individuals over a specified period of time through contribution to economic activities in their daily course of life. Such an inequality can be measured & therefore compared between regions, districts, states, countries or on demographic basis. Wealth inequality can exist as disparity in form of asset holding, estates or investments.

One such way of measuring economic inequalities is the Gini Coefficient. The Gini coefficient shows how far the actual distribution of income or wealth differs from a perfectly equal distribution, there are other approaches to analyze income or wealth shares in which different population portions holdings can be compared. The value ranges from 0 to 1. Closer the coefficient is to 0, the more ‘equal’ the society with respect to the parameter, the score of ‘1’ representing perfect inequality. Another way of measurement, which also aligns with SDG Indicator 10.1 is measuring the proportion of population holding certain percentage of income/wealth of nation. It is often expressed as percentage of the wealth held by top 1% or top 10% of the population. Higher values signify disproportionate distribution, indicative of inequalities in the society.

As economies look to expand in the direction of higher output, productivity, efficiency in use of their resources and the ability to have a better standard of living, often there appears a disparity in how these incomes are distributed. And it is just as fair for a society to have a reasonable distribution of income & wealth and SDG-10 targets exactly in that direction.

As for the state of Gujarat, the economy has grown significantly in the past decades contributing to the Indian Economy. The GSDP or Gross State Domestic Product and per capita income in Gujarat has been greater than the national averages signalling a strong economy in Gujarat. This paper moves beyond looking at the overall economic indicators to looking at how the economic benefits are distributed among in the state of Gujarat.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A study (Raza, 2021) conducted in context of Gujarat examines it as a case study to investigate the factors contributing to the trend in women's representation in the Gujarat State Assembly and the Lok Sabha elections of 2017 and 2019. Despite the notable success of 50 percent reservation for women in local governance structures across the state, this progress has not translated into higher political representation at the state and national levels. While it mentions, that there has been significant groundwork for enhancing women's political participation and has been into place over the past 15 years, the effectiveness of state-led initiatives, it believes depends heavily on robust monitoring and implementation mechanisms.

An analysis of district-level Human Development Indices in Gujarat (Vishwanathan & Bahinipati, 2021) reveals significant disparities across key dimensions such as living standards, access to health infrastructure, and educational attainment. These uneven patterns highlight the need for Gujarat to reassess and realign its development strategies. To promote inclusive growth and improve human development outcomes, the state must prioritize increased public investment in essential sectors such as healthcare infrastructure, quality medical services, nutritional security, education, skill development, and women's empowerment.

According to a study (Shrivastava & Singh, 2011), Gujarat stands out not only as one of India's most industrialized and progressive states but also as one of the most urbanized. The state government has implemented several initiatives aimed at advancing the development of women and children, such as Beti Bachao (Save the Girl Child), Gaurav Nari Niti (Women's Pride), Gender Equality programs etc. These initiatives are in line with **SDG 10**, which emphasizes **inclusive growth** and **gender equality**. The study highlights that Gujarat's focus on sustainable and inclusive growth is supported by integrated policies, along with adequate physical and social infrastructure.

An analysis (Nizamuddin, 2014) on SDG performance of Gujarat indicates that Gujarat's economic performance during the period 2001–02 to 2011–12 was consistently more than the national average. In 2011–12, the state's per capita income—measured as Per Capita Net State Domestic Product (NSDP) at current prices—was estimated at ₹89,668, significantly higher than the all-India average. This reflects Gujarat's had a relatively stronger economic standing during the decade, although per capita may not fully capture disparities in intra-state development and distribution.

Between 1993–94 and 2004–05, an intra-state consumption study showed that inequality rose in several states, including Gujarat, Haryana, Kerala, Odisha, and Punjab. The study (Sahasranaman & Kumar, 2023) examines income distribution patterns across Indian states, with particular attention to the evolution of incomes at the lower end of the distribution. Given the limited availability of state-level data, much of the existing literature on inequality relies on National Sample Survey (NSS) consumption data to analyze inter-state variations in consumption inequality.

A study (Das & Mondal, 2023) assessing income inequality across India and its fifteen major states between 1983 and 2011–12 finds that within-group inequality—specifically within rural and urban areas—contributes more significantly to overall inequality than between-group inequality (i.e., between rural and urban areas). The analysis places particular importance on the implications of these patterns for achieving SDG 10. The study reports a rise in **rural inequality** in Gujarat during this period, highlighting the need for more targeted involvements beyond urban-rural comparisons.

III. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The objectives of the study include:

- (i) To theoretically lay out the existing state of affairs of Gujarat in context to target indicators relevant to **Sustainable Development Goal 10 (SDG-10)**
- (ii) To discuss any insights & implications on the progress from (i) above.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The paper employs a secondary data analysis for the study. Research Articles, existing literature, government reports & websites, articles serve as data sources for the study. For crime statistics, the report on 'Crime in India' (2022) by National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) is utilized for district wise data. The target indicators under the UN SDG-10 goals are more relevant to National context than state level efforts, however, relevant parallels or proxy indicators have been discussed. NITI Aayog's SDG Index provides a framework of relevant indicators, which have been picked up for the purposes of the study.

Indicators 10.1 & 10.2 focus on Income distribution, whereas 10.3 focusses on Inclusion. This has been represented as people having felt discriminated. We source the crime-data for districts of Gujarat against Scheduled Castes (SCs) & Scheduled Tribes (STs) from the NCRB. There is also brief discussion on the financial soundness of the state as presented from the latest state Budget (Indicator 10.5) and on the representation of women and reserved seats in the state assembly as indicator of inclusion. All relevant data points extracted have been cleaned/tabulated and presented suitably for the study. The sources are duly cited for the data tables.

Disclaimer: One needs to exercise caution while interpreting crime statistics. As NCRB, 2022 puts it, "Increase in crime numbers in a State police data may in fact be on account of certain citizen centric police initiatives, like launching of e-FIR facility or women Helpdesks, etc." The assumption of rising crime reports should not be attributed to inefficiency of law & order.

V. DISCUSSION

Estimates on inequality studies (Bharti, Chancel, Piketty, & Somanchi, 2023) suggest that inequality in India fell in the years following independence and its lowest levels may well have been achieved by the early 1980s. However, we have a marked and relentless increase in the concentration of income and wealth trends among the top earners over the subsequent decades, explicitly since the early-2000s. As of 2022–23, the top 1% of the population had an estimated 22.6% of total income, and 40.1% of total wealth held by the top 1%. The estimates indicate that deepening structural inequality is a significant barrier to India's commitments under SDG 10, reducing inequality in between countries. It is unclear if growing an economy reduces inequality, but ideas and mechanisms that push for broader redistribution and inclusive access to opportunity will be needed.

The Niti Aayog SDG India Index provides an idea about the State performance (NITI Aayog, 2024). The state of Gujarat scored **0.19 in the Gini Coefficient**, which is more significantly closer to 0, but still reflective of inequalities in place. The ideal target is 0. It mentions that approximately 50% of seats in the Panchayati Institutions are occupied by women. Although this isn't conclusive of any fact of equality, but sure deserves appreciation on a surface level insight.

Approximately 22% of the seats are occupied by people from SC/ST segment of population reflective of their representation in the State Assembly. The overall performance puts it in the front runner category of all the states analyzed. It is not although among the top 5 scoring states in this domain.

Indicators 10.1 & 10.2 deal with distribution of income. The best way to deal with the study of income distribution is through measures such as Gini Coefficients & proportional measurement of top 10 or 20% richest population. Although at state level, such data is not very easily available to obtain a reliable income distribution, we briefly discuss and present the existing facts about income, represented by the State GDP. The following is the GSDP trend of Gujarat over past decade as extracted from the IBEF Website.

Chart 1 – GSDP of Gujarat (2015 to 2024) : Current Prices

Note: BE- Budget Estimate

Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics Gujarat, Government of Gujarat

Gujarat remains one of India’s foremost industrialized states. For the fiscal year 2023–24, its Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) at current prices is estimated at ₹25.63 trillion (approximately US\$309.54 billion), reflecting a growth rate of 13.36% over the previous year. In 2022–23, Gujarat accounted for 8.6% of India’s total GDP, underscoring its significant contribution to the national economy. (IBEF, 2024)

As can be clearly noticed, the upward trend of state income is characterized by a compounded growth of 10.49%. The numbers are calculated on nominal basis.

As per the recent state budget of Gujarat state, Gujarat’s economic momentum continues to remain strong, with its Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) for 2025–26 projected at ₹29.82 lakh crore—reflecting a 12% increase over the revised estimates for 2024–25. In 2023–24, the state’s per capita GSDP stood at ₹3,36,875, marking a 9% rise from the previous year. (PRS India, 2025). Although such significant increments are indicative of rising economic power, it is always upon the details of the disparities to be investigated to decide upon existence of inequalities. Financial soundness is another target indicator as laid down under Goal 10.5

Another sub-Indicator target that we discuss deals with the Seats reserved or the count of women in parliament. The representation of inclusiveness is also driven by the fact that all the sections of the society get appropriate position and ability to voice their decision-making power. As per the rules laid down for elections to assembly & local Panchayati raj positions, reservations are made suitably for SCs & STs. Of the 182 seats, 13 are reserved for the SCs and 27 for the STs. The 2022 State Assembly elections show, 40 women were fielded from different parties for the election, and 15 won them. The effective representation thereby results as approximately 8.2% which is low.

Indicator 10.3 talks about Proportion of People having felt or having reported discrimination. It is important that all the sections of the society feel included and respected. Discrimination on any ground such as caste, creed, gender, religion or otherwise hampers the social structure. It is important to ensure justice and maintain control on any cases that demean or harm basic human dignity.

In this context we use data from NCRB district wise report, for Crime against SC & ST under the relevant domain The case rates (relative to population) are tabulated below:

Table 1: Crime Rate (SC) : Gujarat State (Value > 25)

Sr. No	District/Region	Crime Against SCs
1	Ahmedabad City	185
2	Ahmedabad Rural	53
3	Amreli	47
4	Anand	27
5	Banaskantha	71
6	Gandhinagar	47
7	Jamnagar	30
8	Junagadh	33
9	Kachchh West	69
10	Kheda	64
11	Mehsana	44
12	Patan	29
13	Porbandar	28
14	Rajkot City	62
15	Rajkot Rural	55
16	Sabarkantha	27
17	Surat City	34
18	Surendranagar	50
19	Vadodara City	33
20	Vadodara Rural	41
	Total (Gujarat)	1214

Source: NCRB Report (2022)

Maximum was reported from Ahmedabad city, followed by Banaskantha district. Gujarat reported 1214 in total.

Table 2: Crime Rate (ST) : Gujarat State (value >10)

Sr. No	District/Region	Crime Against STs
1	Ahmedabad City	17
2	Banaskantha	21
3	Bharuch	40
4	Gandhinagar	11
5	Narmada	12

6	Panchmahal	39
7	Rajkot City	12
8	Sabarkantha	16
9	Surat City	16
10	Surat Rural	24
11	Vadodara Rural	37
	Total (Gujarat)	322

Source: NCRB Report (2022)

Maximum was reported from Bharuch region, followed by Panchmahal district. Gujarat reported 322 in total.

While crime rate data presents a very different insight through which we can observe social inequality and regions which require more attention. The concept of structural inequality or economic justice, access to public service access, representation & inclusiveness are core to the SDG-10 mission. Over time, several debates have come up regarding redistribution of income style schemes. Gujarat has displayed an overall decent score of 68 in the State Index score by NITI Aayog. The ratio of participation of women to men in technical & professional capacities is also decent (NITI Aayog, 2024).

SDG 10 targets require that we should not only should we focus on ideas on redistribute income and economic power but that we ensure that all segments of the society benefit from the targeted actions taken by the government. All sections of the demographic are benefitted from the growth story.

In working towards this, it would be helpful for Gujarat to take a regional-specific approach. It would also benefit to collect more data, to better identify intra-state variation. It is important that we understand the links between welfare schemes and their results. With technology advancements & digital monitoring, one could also improve transparency and ensure that benefits reach intended audience. These suggestions can help advance Gujarat (and also India) in the direction to a more participatory, all-inclusive, comprehensive development.

VI. CONCLUSION

Although Gujarat continues to lead its path as a showcase of fast economic growth, the existing challenge of equity-based outcomes will continue to remain key to achieving the SDG 10 agenda. This paper from a theoretical perspective, shows that there is still quite a path that needs to be walked & addressed. Structural inequalities are often difficult to discern on limited data, and they often get masked within indicators. Without disaggregated state-level data, the paper still manages to provide a fair overview of the existing state of inequality in the state and the policies. As India continues to adapt to the commitment to the SDGs, case studies—like this on the state of Gujarat—will offer opportunities to investigate & compare more in detail about inherent issues at micro levels. Ultimately, the goal of reducing inequalities has to extend beyond tracking national performance. This would require tracking and recording data at local levels, with an active involvement from the administration and society at large. This study gave a preliminary understanding through an economic eye, of how the goals of reducing inequality intersects with that of achieving inclusive progress.

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